

Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide as a brominating agent for the bromination of metal(II) complexes of Schiff base derived from acetylacetone and *p*-anisidine

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Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PyHBr₃) is used as a brominating agent for the bromination of the Schiff base chelates of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and zinc(II) derived from acetylacetone and *p*-anisidine under acidic and ammoniacal conditions at room temperature. Under ammoniacal condition these complexes [M(H-acpa)₂] where M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II}; H-acpa = Schiff base derived from acetylacetone and *p*-anisidine] undergo easy γ -bromination to give electrophilic bromopropduct, M(Br-acpa)₂ but in acidic medium they undergo chelate ring cleavage to give [MBr₄][PyH]₂. The structure of these complexes has been characterised by microanalytical data, IR, UV-Vis and ¹H NMR data.

In continuation of our work on Schiff base derived from acetylacetone and *p*-anisidine¹, we herein report the bromination of these chelates using pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide.

Results and discussion

The analytical data along with some physical properties of the new compounds are summarised in Table 1. The analytical data of the complexes correspond to the general formula M(H-acpa)₂ which are similar to the data as reported earlier¹. At room temperature under ammoniacal medium the electrophilic brominated complexes formed have the

general formula M(Br-acpa)₂, while in acidic medium they have the general formula [MBr₄][PyH]₂. These chelates, M(H-acpa)₂ and M(Br-acpa)₂ show no appreciable conductance (10⁻⁴ M in DMSO solvent). But, the conductance values of the nucleophilic bromo complexes (10⁻⁴ M in DMSO solvent), [MBr₄][PyH]₂ are in the range of 159–165 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which show that they are electrolytes. The magnetic susceptibility values of the complexes M(H-acpa)₂ and M(Br-acpa)₂ at room temperature are consistent with that of square-planar geometry around the metal ion². In order to study the binding mode of Schiff base to metal in the complexes, IR spectrum of the free ligand was compared with the spectra of the metal complexes. The ligand shows its characteristics -C=N in the region 1620 cm⁻¹ which is shifted to lower frequency in all the metal complexes in the region 1600–1580 cm⁻¹. This lower absorption indicates the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal which may be due to the influence of the electron donating nature of *p*-methoxy substitution. The metal chelates show some new bands in the region 480–450 and 400–350 cm⁻¹ which are due to formation of M–O and M–N bonds respectively³.

Comparison of the IR spectra of the substrate chelates with that of electrophilic bromo- β -diketoamine products reveals that due to bromination of C–H bond becoming C–Br bond, the weak band at 1195 cm⁻¹ and the medium intensity band at 795 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the in-plane bending ($\delta_{\text{C-H}}$) and out-plane bending ($\pi_{\text{C-H}}$) respectively⁴ disappeared in the spectra of the γ -substituted brominated com-

Table 1. Analytical data of the compounds*

Compd.	Colour	Metal%		Conductivity (in DMSO) ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		Found	(Calcd.)	
[CuBr ₄][PyH] ₂	Green	11.6	(11.7)	159
[CoBr ₄][PyH] ₂	Blue	10.5	(10.8)	169
[NiBr ₄][PyH] ₂	Green	10.5	(10.9)	162
[ZnBr ₄][PyH] ₂	Yellow	11.4	(11.9)	164
Cu(Br-acpa) ₂	Red	9.0	(9.3)	–
Co(Br-acpa) ₂	Green	8.5	(8.7)	–
Ni(Br-acpa) ₂	Red	9.2	(9.5)	–
Cu(H-acpa) ₂	Red	12.4	(12.7)	–
Ni(H-acpa) ₂	Pale green	11.3	(11.9)	–
Co(H-acpa) ₂	Green	11.4	(11.6)	–
Zn(H-acpa) ₂	Colourless	12.3	(12.5)	–

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Br analyses.

plexes. The chelate ring cleavage product $[\text{MBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$ exhibits characteristic bands one at 3070 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and another band at 750 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\delta_{\text{N-H}}$. The data also show that there is no band at 1600 cm^{-1} indicating the absence of C=O group and this confirms the presence of pyridinium moiety in the nucleophilic substituted bromoproduct.

Further, the coordination of the Schiff base was confirmed from its ^1H NMR data. The ^1H NMR spectrum of brominated product of Zn^{II} complex provides further evidence for the formation of $[\text{MBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$ and electrophilic bromo product. The complex, $\text{Zn}(\text{H-acpa})_2$ shows signal at δ 1.7 due to vinyl methyl peak and δ 7.1–7.3 assigned to phenyl group and $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ proton shows at δ 5.1. But, its electrophilic bromo product i.e. $\text{Zn}(\text{Br-acpa})_2$ does not give any signal at δ 5.1. So, the product confirms the bromination which occurs at $\gamma_{\text{C-H}}$ bond, whereas its nucleophilic bromo product, $[\text{ZnBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$ shows a signal at δ 8.3 due to N-H group and δ 8.8 corresponding to pyridinium ring and δ 9.1 indicates C-H proton.

The electronic absorption spectra of the Schiff base and its Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were recorded at room temperature using DMSO as solvent. $\text{Cu}(\text{Br-acpa})_2$ shows a broad band at 21880 cm^{-1} due to $^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow ^2\text{A}_{1g}$ transition which supports square-planar geometry whereas $[\text{CoBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$ exhibits absorption maximum at 16360 cm^{-1} corresponding to $^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow ^4\text{T}_1$ transition which indicates a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

Conclusion :

The use of PyHBr_3 as a brominating agent appears advantageous over other brominating agents because bromination using PyHBr_3 is faster and occurs at room temperature. However, the nature of the end products with PyHBr_3 is dictated by the nature of the reaction medium.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The brominating agent, PyHBr_3 was prepared according to the literature procedure⁵. The molar conductivity of the complexes was measured on a Systronic model-305 digital direct reading conductivity meter using DMSO as solvent. IR spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes in CDCl_3 were recorded on a Bruker instrument using TMS as internal standard. The UV-Vis spectra of all the complexes were recorded in DMSO on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of Schiff base :

An ethanolic (20 ml) solution of *p*-anisidine (0.1 M, 12.3 g) was refluxed with acetylacetone (0.1 M, 10.2 ml) for about 4 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to one-third. The reaction mixture on ice-cooling gave orange-yellow semisolid (H-acpa) which was preserved in a desiccator. Yield 60%; m.p. 86°C .

Synthesis of complexes :

An ethanolic (20 ml) solution of Schiff base (2.05 g, 0.01 M) was refluxed with metal(II) salt (0.005 M) in ethanol for 2 h. After refluxing, the volume of the solution was reduced to one-third. The solid product $[\text{M}(\text{H-acpa})_2]$ obtained was filtered and washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Bromination of metal complexes :

To an ethanolic (10 ml) solution of metal(II) Schiff base complexes (0.01 mol) was mixed with an ethanolic (10 ml) solution of PyHBr_3 (0.02 mol) with constant stirring. A few drops of NH_3 was added and the product got precipitated within a few minutes. The solid bromoproduct $[\text{M}(\text{Br-acpa})_2]$ was filtered and successively washed with chloroform and dried *in vacuo*. The analogous reaction was attempted with metal(II) Schiff base complexes in acidic condition to isolate $[\text{MBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$.

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